

HOUSING@21.EU: Emerging forms of housing and living in 21st century Europe
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FINAL REPORT: Web-based learning platform

The web platform which is here described has been created for this IP project by the research group ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull (www.salleurl.edu/arc). It consists of two different domains:

1. the web-based learning environment to carry out cases of study collaboratively (www.housing21eu.net; login: guest; password: guest)
2. the web site of the Workshop (www.housing21eu.net/workshop; no login necessary).

The platform has been programmed with DTHML, using CGI-scripts written in Perl, accessing a MySQL database. It is hosted at the server of Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle, and it has a .net domain name, which has been registered for this IP.

1. CASES OF STUDY (www.housing21eu.net)

This environment has been conceived to promote exchange and collaboration of ideas and works among participants. In this regard, it is more than an on-line database: it is a web-based learning platform suited to the pedagogic goals of this IP.

The environment is structured in the following modes:

- SYSTEM. Report of the system activity, organized by day/week.
- INSERT [+]. Interfaces to input cases of study, groups.
- CASES OF STUDY [C]. Graphical and textual documentation of a selected housing case.
- KEYWORDS [K]. Critical vocabulary of concepts associated to the cases of study
- GROUPING [G]. Interfaces to establish associations between cases of study.
- BIBLIOGRAPHY [B]. References and information sources used in the cases of study (books, articles, URL's)
- FORUM [F] On-line discussions about cases of study.
- STUDENT [S] Summary of work submitted by student and by school.

The following description summarizes the functionalities of the different modes. This information is also available on-line at <http://www.housing21eu.net/reports/eu/website1.html>

HOME PAGE. It contains general information for the public, regarding objectives, partners and activities. It provides access to authorized users through LOGIN.

SYSTEM MODE. After logging in, the NEWS section shows the news for the current week. Selecting the other categories in the header (Case studies, Keywords, Forum) shows all entries for each category submitted during the current week. The menu on the left side allows retrieving information entered in the previous weeks.

INSERT MODE. The process to enter a new Case of Study is divided into two steps. First, the basic information is introduced in an input form (title, architect, location...) and the case is recorded. The user can proceed then to enter additional information, step-by-step. For instance, entering "Graphic information" (e.g. representative plans, sections, photos,...) of the case study. For each item described in the menu (Graphic data, Levels, Dimensions, Bibliography, URL, Keywords), the user can enter additional information at any time.

INSERT MODE. Student's reflections regarding the selected case study are collected under the headers LEVELS and DIMENSIONS. There are three levels of analysis of a housing project: social, economical and technological. And there are three dimensions of housing to be described: individual, communal and urban. KEYWORDS are categories freely proposed by the user, which describe the properties of a case of study.

CASE OF STUDY MODE. Visualization of all the information of a selected case of study. The right column displays the KEYWORDS associated with it.

CASE OF STUDY MODE. The right side menu shows the icons of associated cases sharing a keyword with the selected one. This way, it is possible to navigate through the study case library in an associative manner, jumping from case to case, following the chain of associated keywords.

CASE OF STUDY MODE. A Forum can be opened for each single case of study. Comments are recorded in one single thread.

KEYWORD MODE. Cases of study sharing a keyword can be seen in the KEYWORD MODE. The list of keywords on the right menu can be sorted alphabetically or by number or associated cases. Clicking on the icon leads to the CASE OF STUDY MODE.

STUDENT MODE. Participating students are listed by name on the left menu. This list can be ordered alphabetically (A), by University (U), or all students from all Universities (G). Clicking on the photo of a student shows the individual student view (see below).

STUDENT MODE: INDIVIDUAL STUDENT. This view summarizes all the work done by a student, at an individual level (case studies, keywords, ...) and at a collaborative level (adding items to other cases, entries to the Forums...). The information is divided in two blocks. The first block shows the study cases submitted by the students, and the items added to them by other students (in red, with the name of the student who did the entry). The second block underneath shows all contributions that the student has made to other cases. This way, a student can quickly have an overview of the items that other students are adding to the data he or she has entered.

CREATE GROUP. The interface to make groups shows all images stored in the study case library, organized by category (plans, sections, elevations, perspectives, photos). In order to make a group, first a category must be chosen.

CREATE GROUP. All images existing at the database are collected in this interface. After clicking on an icon, a viewer is opened, showing all images of the selected case, sequentially.

CREATE GROUP. To make a group with the selected images, icons are dragged on the hot area underneath. Icons can be put in and out of this area.

CREATE GROUP. After the items forming a group have been chosen, the following information must be introduced: the name of the group and the description of the characteristics of the group (what the selected cases have in common).

GROUP MODE. The "G" in the main menu opens the Group mode, where all groups created are listed. By clicking on one icon leads to the CASE OF STUDY mode.

CASE OF STUDY MODE. The groups in which the selected case is included, appear listed on the right side menu, in much the same way as the keywords.

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>> Bibliography

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[Madraze, L.] S C K G B F

BIBLIOGRAPHY MODE. All bibliographic references -sorted by author (A) or publication date (Y)- associated with the cases can be accessed in this mode.

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>> Forum: NEMEAUSU...

- 16/06/2004 Kanafani, K.
I agree, that the architect should give the inhabitants the possibility of personalizing their territories. But, at least, one aspect of personalization already is the peoples choice of a specific apartment itself. They can (of course not everybody) choose a building with an industrial facade or one with wooden cladding.

- 28/05/2004 Moskal, J.
I think that the requirement of esthetics, steering architect's sense, usually is not able to satisfy individual requirements of inhabitants.

- 23/05/2004 Pavlova, A.
I would like to share an opinion, based on a personal experience. I visited these buildings two years ago and I was surprised to see them after being occupied for fifteen years. The quality of the used materials was very good, but unfortunately they didn't look as in the magazines. The reason for this is mainly the way people appropriate the space they live in. I think that the way the architect has treated the appearance of the building, the architectural style being extremely particular and present, doesn't give the freedom of occupants to personalize the space. Unfortunately, it happens very often that contemporary apartments look better empty than occupied. I would like to question the architects' freedom to design a space with no place for occupant's personality. In this case, using steel garage doors and round windows, Jean Nouvel emphasizes the fact that the building's concept is based on prefabrication, low cost and recycling, but do people who live there would like to think about it every time they want to put a picture on the wall? Hopefully my question will be a subject of an interesting discussion. Thank you.

ADD

[Madraze, L.] S C K G B F

- 28 DWELL... [2]
- 3D CITY [5]
- ARAB HOU... [5]
- ASILE PL... [2]
- BEDZED ... [2]
- CHATEAU... [1]
- CUBIC HO... [1]
- FAMILIST... [1]
- GIFU KIT... [2]
- HOUSE FO... [1]
- HUPEISEN... [1]
- KARL MAR... [1]
- MISS SAR... [1]
- MULTIFUN... [1]
- NEMEAUSU... [8]**
- SILODAM [2]
- THE GUES... [1]
- UNITÉ D... [1]
- UNITÉ D... [1]
- WALDEN [1]
- WOHNBAU ... [1]

FORUM MODE. All active forums can be quickly accessed in this mode. Inputs can be made in much the same way as in the study case mode.

2. WORKSHOP WEBSITE (www.housing21eu.net/workshop)

This web site was used before, during and after the workshop. It was published one month before the workshop started, so participants could get acquainted with the sites selected to make design proposals. This way, participants could know brief, references, time table and group organization in advance. During the workshop, the web site was used to record the development of ideas discussed in the group meetings, which were posted in a Weblog. After the workshop, it was used by students to present their design proposals.

ENTRY PAGE. Home page of the Workshop web page, with a direct access to the students design proposals.

SITE DESCRIPTION. Each one of the three sites was described by means of plans, images and panoramic views.

PROJECT PRESENTATION. Each group has presented the project on the web with a series of images, described with a short text.

WEBLOG. Reflections after the group meetings were posted in the site Weblog, both by students and faculty. The Weblog was structured in the six categories that make up the conceptual framework of the subject of study of this IP: social, economic and technological transforming factors; and individual, communal and urban dimensions of dwelling.